

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

Full paper

STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

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Citation: Möller, T., van den Besselaar, P., & Mom, C. (2022). What is researcher independence and how can it be measured?. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti2292). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6975312>

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26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

What is researcher independence and how can it be measured?¹

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Introduction

‘Independence’ is a core criterion in selecting grant or job applicants. In this paper we develop – after a theoretical introduction – a few indicators for independence that can be calculated also for large datasets. After having done so, we apply the indicators to two cases of prestigious early career grants. We end with ideas for follow-up work to further develop the indicators.

Independence

For many selection procedures in science, such as the prestigious ERC starting grant and the German Emmy Noether program, independence is mentioned as a review criterion. But what does the concept of independence mean? We propose that independence relates with negative freedom (*freedom from*) and with positive freedom (*freedom to*), a distinction developed in the philosophical discourse on freedom of action.² The negative freedom is the *freedom from* influences, especially from other actors (personal or organizational) or constraints. This freedom is “negative” because it is undetermined what a person does with the *freedom from* and how he or she then acts concretely. This is where the term positive freedom comes in, as the freedom of a person to act (in a self-determined direction). Negative freedom can be understood as a precondition for positive freedom, as *freedom from* enables *freedom to*. The realized particular action makes other potential options no longer possible. In this respect, actions limit the scope of further actions. These *path dependencies* are not perceived by the self-determined actors as a restriction of their scope of action, but as a realization of their *freedom to* go their own way. Positive freedom in this sense does not mean to keep all paths open and to live in a free-floating unboundedness. Martin Heidegger, for example, distinguishes in this respect between a “freedom as unbound, *freedom from* (negative freedom)” and a “freedom as being bound to, *libertas determinationis, freedom to* (positive freedom)” (Heidegger, 1971, p. 106).

¹ This work was supported by grant nr. 824574 of the EC: The GRANteD project (2019-2023).

² The difference between freedom of will and freedom of action will not be discussed here. However, the concept of negative and positive freedom can also be applied to freedom of will.

We apply the above distinction to the concept of researcher independence. In the following we distinguish between *independence from* other actors or constraints, e.g. the doctoral supervisor or the university in which one works, and an *independence to* develop one's own research agenda and to undertake that research.

In this sense, researcher independence means both breaking ties (*independence from*) and entering into new ties (*independence to*). This point is important to emphasize as independence should not be interpreted as the lowest number of ties. Being an independent researcher in a world of team science does not mean doing research alone, but having the *freedom to* choose the collaborations that are most appropriate for one's particular research agenda. Independence should not be confused with disconnectedness.

In the academic literature and in practical guidelines, various definitions of researcher independence can be found that more or less comprise the above distinction without making it explicit. For example, the Research Excellence Framework Guidance on Submission defines an independent researcher as someone who “undertakes self-directed research, rather than carrying out another individual’s research programme” (REF Guidance, 2019, p. 118). The definition implies that *independence from* “carrying out another individual’s research programme” is a prerequisite for *independence to* “undertake self-directed research”.

Documents about academic career development refer to a process of *becoming independent* instead of *being independent*. A guidebook from a research-oriented university states: “Research degrees are training in independent research” (Code of Practice, cited by Guccione 2020). It could be summarized that from entering a university as a student, through the positions of a doctoral student, postdoc, senior scientist, and assistant/associate/full professor, the independence evolves and increases. We assume that successful academics show an increasing *independence from* and *independence to* at each stage, although independence above a certain level may not necessary always better (Gläser, et al., 2021). We agree with this view, but consider the distinction between *independence from* and *independence to* is useful to answer the question at what career stage what degree of independence is appropriate.

Summarizing, the distinction between negative and positive freedom (*freedom from* and *freedom to*) borrowed from philosophy can be profitably applied to the question of researcher independence. It focuses on the process of becoming independent, instead of being independent, which can be analyzed in terms of researchers' career development over time, in which a co-evolution of *independence from* and *independence to* seems to be most conducive. Furthermore, defining independence in this way shows that researcher independence is not contradictory to collaborative research and team science.

Earlier work

Elsewhere, we have developed the concept of independence in relation to the PhD supervisors, as this is the initial dependent collaboration relation that early career researchers engage in (Van den Besselaar & Sandström 2019). After graduating, the postdoc period is then seen as the period to start developing research independence, which should result in new collaborations and new research topics. We translated that concept in terms of indicators and tested those on a small sample of researchers. The following indicators were proposed:

1. Becoming independent means that the role of the former supervisors should become less prominent in the collaboration network of the early career researcher, which can be measured through the *eigenvector centrality* of the researcher and the *clustering coefficient* of the

supervisor(s). This is in terms of the previous section: becoming “independent from” the supervisor’s network and “independent to” create an own network.

2. Becoming independent also means the role of former *supervisor(s) as coauthor* declines – which can be measured by dividing the number of the publications of the researcher without supervisors as coauthor by all publications of the researcher. In terms of the previous section: becoming “independent from” the supervisor and “independent to” publish.

3. Finally, an independent researcher is expected to enter in *new research topics*, different from those of the environment where the PhD research was obtained. To calculate this, we retrieved all publications of the supervisor(s) and the researcher from WoS, did some topic mapping of the set of publications, and then calculated the share of independent topics. This is in terms of the previous section: becoming “independent from” the supervisor’s themes and “independent to” develop an own research agenda.

A disadvantage is that the calculation of indicators 1 and 3 is time-consuming, and therefore we propose to use slightly different indicators.

Large scale indicators: concepts, data and methods

Independent publications: We produced a script that splits the publications of a young researcher into two groups: those with and those without any of the supervisors as co-author. The query basically looks in the author-name or Scopus authors-ID-field which contains the name or the IDs of all the co-authors. If one of the names or IDs belongs to one of the supervisors, this paper is counted as ‘dependent’. In case none of the supervisor IDs is found in the mentioned field, the paper is counted as ‘independent’. One can do this for full papers and for fractional paper counts, but that seems to make no difference. And it can be done for different periods in the career, in order to be able to investigate the development of independence over time. Basically, this leads to the formula:

$$\text{Independence} = (\text{Number independent publications}) / (\text{All publications}) \quad (1)$$

Independent research topics: A second script was developed to find all research topics in which the former PhD student has published without any of the supervisors as co-author. Here we use Scopus Scival data, and one has the choice between about 40 fields of research, some 1,500 topic clusters, and about 96,000 topics³. We decided to do this analysis at the level of *topic clusters*, as topics are too fine-grained (as we would have more topics than papers in the analysis).

Technically, this means that we need to identify the set of *topic clusters* in which the former PhD student has been publishing, and then identify the subset of those topic clusters in which one or more of the supervisors have been publishing (with or without co-authoring with the former PhD student). The remaining subset (so the topic clusters in which the supervisors are not visible) can be counted as the independent topic clusters. However, one could argue that in cases where the former PhD student first published in a topic cluster without the supervisor as co-author, that those topic clusters should also be counted as independent. We indeed include both sets of topic clusters in the *independent topic cluster set*. We did not use a threshold for the period between the former PhD student entering a topic cluster and a supervisor entering that topic cluster. Again, this can be done for different periods in the career. The indicator would be:

$$\text{Independence} = (\text{Number of independent topics}) / (\text{all topics}) \quad (2)$$

³ Source: <https://www.elsevier.com/solutions/scival/features/topic-prominence-in-science>

We applied the derived indicators on two cases, both of early career researchers during the PhD period and the early postdoc period.

Calculating the indicators: an example from the Netherlands

We use a dataset of 899 researchers who received their PhD from the same Dutch university between 2000 and 2014, in fields where journal articles are the main output medium. Bibliometric data were also collected for 812 supervisors, this set of PhD students had on average 2.05 supervisors ($sd = 1.24$). We use Scopus/Scival data, because every record (paper) contains a field with *all author-identifiers*.⁴ Another advantage of Scival is the *very detailed research topic classification*. The data were manually collected and cleaned.

We produced a script that splits the publications of a researcher into two groups: those with and those without any of the supervisors as coauthor. We then calculated the independence indicator for the PhD period⁵, and for the whole career (up to 2018). The latter is important, as one may expect an optimal career pattern where the researcher is very close to (and dependent on) the supervisors during the PhD period, as that may lead to the strongest learning effect, and then becoming independent in the later part of the early career. Becoming independent too early may be disadvantageous. We also use fractionally counted papers.

A second script was developed to find all research topics in which the former PhD student has published without any of the supervisors as co-author. Also here we use Scival data on 1,500 topic clusters.

Table 1 shows that average independence in terms of *published papers* almost doubles from the PhD period to the later career, from 0.27 to 0.47. Independence in terms of *research topics* was very low during the PhD period (0.035), which is expected as the PhD period is about learning to do research and then one would expect a PhD student being embedded in the research lines of the supervisors. Topical independence increases strongly in the later career.

Table 1. Share of the independent papers and topics (the PhD period and career)

	Period	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	N
Papers (fractional)	PhD period	0.2750	0.3296	0	1	925
Papers (fractional)	Career	0.4574	0.3511	0	1	925
Topics	PhD period	0.0345	0.1186	0	1	925
Topics	Career	0.3352	0.3191	0	1	925

Table 2 shows, the correlation between the two career-indicators is moderate⁶ (.577), but for the PhD period, the correlation between two indicators is rather weak (.266), suggesting that independence develops in two stages: first own papers, then in the later career own topics. ‘Own’ here does not mean single authored, but independent from the supervisors.

Table 2. Correlations between the independent indicators

	Career: topics	PhD period: Papers (frac)	PhD period topics
Career: papers (frac)	.577*	.692*	.170*
Career: topics		.417*	.248*
PhD period: papers (frac)			.266*

* Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). N=925

⁴ Several PhD students and supervisors have more than one ID, which we merged.

⁵ Defined as the three years before until the three years after the year of obtaining the PhD degree.

⁶ See e.g.: <https://www.statstutor.ac.uk/resources/uploaded/pearsons.pdf> (Evans 1996)

Figures 1 and 2 show the frequency distributions of the independence indicators. (i) Quite a large share of the PhD students has an independence score of 0. (ii) The relative high frequency of the score 1 is due to the PhD students with only one publication, without supervisors as co-authors. (iii) Over time, early career researchers tend to become more independent, and the number of researchers that score 0 declines considerably, and all other values increase. However, quite a few remain rather dependent. This latter group may contain researchers that left the science system. Such an analysis could be done easily, using ‘stopping to publish’ as indicator for leaving the research system.

Figure 1. Independence PhD period (papers) Figure 2. Independence career (papers)

Figures 3 and 4 show the distributions for the topics-based indicators. The figures show that topical independence is overall lower than paper-based independence, which is expected. This suggests that many of the papers not co-authored with supervisors still remain in the same topic clusters. Finally, and also as expected, independence increases strongly over the career (Figure 4 versus Figure 3) but many researchers remain in the same topics as their supervisors worked (which again includes those PhD students that left the science system after graduating).

Figure 3. Independence PhD (topics)

Figure 4. Independence career (topics)

This shows that using Scopus/Scival enables the calculation of the independence indicators at a large scale. We do not enter here in the discussion whether the deployed *Scival topic clusters* (Scopus 2018) are accurate, as even when the topic classification is not perfect, it can be used as to calculate the field overlap between the early career researcher and the PhD supervisor. This avoids that we have to manually produce field maps for every individual PhD student and his/her supervisor(s), as was done in the earlier paper (Van den Besselaar & Sandstrom 2019). In the next section we apply the indicators on a second case, to explore whether independence explains partly grant success.

Applying the indicators, an example from Germany

Researcher independence is a central review criterion for the Emmy Noether Program of the German Research Foundation (DFG). The program is open to academics from all fields who have completed their doctorate with an outstanding result and submitted an excellent research proposal within four years after the date of dissertation. They should have published demanding articles in internationally renowned journals and have already proven their scientific independence and substantial international research experience in the postdoctoral period (Böhmer, Hornbostel & Meuser, 2008, p. 18). Our data cover funding decisions between 2000 and 2006 in biology, chemistry and physics, and consist of 328 Emmy Noether (predominantly male) applicants (table 5).

The success rate in the period under consideration is relatively high (56.7%, table 5), which is probably mainly due to the high formal entry requirements. After easing the rules, the success rate dropped to the current 20% (DFG 2021). In the basic population (table 6), the average age of the applicants was 32.6 years. The doctorate was awarded at an average age of 29.1 years. The applicants submitted their proposal 3.5 years after receiving their doctorate. Women are on average half a year younger at the time of their doctorate and half a year older at the time of their application.

Table 5. All applicants (population)

N=328	male	female	sum
granted	47.0%	9.8%	56.7%
not granted	32.6%	10.7%	43.3%
sum	79.6%	20.4%	

Table 6. Used sample (supervisors known)

N=107	Male	female	sum
granted	65.4%	7.5%	72.9%
not granted	23.4%	3.7%	27.1%
sum	88.8%	11.2%	

The doctoral theses were searched via the German National Library. Then the names of the supervisors were investigated, through (where available) (i) the metadata from the German National Library, (ii) names of supervisors from the online publications of the doctoral thesis or (iii) from an internet search of the applicants. The first two methods yielded hardly any hits, and also the internet search hardly found names of the supervisors, and if so, usually only that of the first supervisor. This leads to a selection bias, since persons who left the scientific system could not be found on the internet or did not have names of their supervisors on their homepages. All data required for the analysis could only be found for 107 researchers. Successful male applicants were overrepresented in this sample (table 6).

For those 107 applicants all publications were retrieved from Scopus by using the Scopus author IDs. When researchers have several IDs (Aman 2018; Kawashima & Tomizawa 2015), we merged the IDs. In the following analyses, the first (collaboration) *independence* indicator was applied (see above, both full and fractional count). The value of the independence indicator ranges from 0 (no independent publication) to 1 (all publications without the supervisor). The indicator is calculated for three periods: (i) publications up to and including the year of the PhD thesis, (ii) publications up to and including the year of application, and (iii) publications up to four years after application.

The researcher *independence* is lowest during the doctorate and increases step by step thereafter (fig 5). This seems to fulfil a central assumption of the independence model, namely that researchers become more and more independent over time. Furthermore, full and fractional counts hardly differ (Pearson's correlation: 0.95).

A logistic regression model was tested with grant success as the dependent variable and independence, gender and subject as independent variables. The findings suggest that independence has no effect on early career grant decisions (Table 6) even if it is a formal review criterion and *independence from* the supervisor increases over time (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Independence indicator for publications in three time periods

Table 6. Grant success by independence*, gender and subject** of the applicants

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	1.6014	0.5845	2.740	0.00615
Independence (full count)	-0.7082	0.7309	-0.969	0.33260
Gender female	-0.3082	0.6675	-0.462	0.64423
Subject Chemistry	-0.2865	0.5601	-0.512	0.60893
Subject Physics	-0.2627	0.5522	-0.476	0.63425

Logistic regression; *: full count & publications until the year of application;

** : Biology, Chemistry, Physics.

The case illustrates how the independence indicator can be used, although the above findings (table 6) are not yet final. In a follow up analysis, we will include other variables in the model that may influence the selection process such as past performance. Another issue that need to be solved is that we do not have all information about supervisors for all applicants, which leads to an overestimation of independence. This also affects the sample size and may lead to a selection bias.

Conclusions

The paper shows that large scale calculating of independence indicators is possible, using Scopus data. The main data-issue is identifying the PhD supervisors, which is not always easy. One solution might be to take the dominant co-author of the PhD period as the (informal) supervisor. The dominant co-author can be identified quite easily, and it is not unlikely that this is the formal supervisor.

With respect to the independence model and the independence indicator(s), we showed (Figure 5) that the *independence from* the supervisor (or other senior researchers) indicator is already a good indication of the way the independence of junior researchers advances. Other indicators could be developed, to measure different dimensions of independence: *(in)dependence from* research infrastructures / labs, and *independence to* enter other infrastructures or to create an own lab. Also the *independence to* create own collaborations through international mobility could be measured. Finally, for a reliable measurement, we may need an underlying variable that is based on such larger set of independence related indicators.

Acknowledgement

The work for this paper was supported by grant nr. 824574 of the EC: The GRANteD project (2019-2023).

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